

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE WORK OF TEACHER ARTIST KOMILJON OTANIYAZOV IN THE EDUCATION AND SPIRITUALIZATION OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS AND EDUCATORS

Rajabov Shakhzodbek Bakhrom ugli

Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the Department of Art History

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Abstract: This article narrates the life and work of Komiljon Otaniyozov, a prominent figure in Uzbek music, a folk artist, and an educator. It highlights Otaniyozov's deep love for music, his contributions to the fields of art and pedagogy, as well as his role in preserving the national musical heritage. The author emphasizes Otaniyozov's creative endeavors and his significant role in teaching the younger generation to cherish patriotism, love for their homeland, and human values.

Keywords: Uzbek musical art, musician, singer, educator, Performance Excellence, Music Heritage, classical music, musical education.

Introduction.

Komiljon Otaniyozov is a musician, singer, teacher, pedagogue, and a great artist who left an indelible mark on Uzbek music. His unique teaching is manifested in his perfection in performance, enthusiasm, and dedication to educating his students. The valuable thoughts he expressed about what a modern musician-artist should be are a vivid proof of this: "...An artist should be educated, knowledgeable, and a person who feels the words and the lyrics from the heart." He must fully understand the content, spirit, melody, and pain of the lyrics. A poet does not write a poem by playing, but fills it with pain, passion, and intellectual elegance. Therefore, an artist can convey it to the listener only if he can sing with such pain, passion, and elegance. A word and melody from the heart reach other hearts..."

As teacher Komiljon Otaniyozov emphasized, today every teacher, especially a music teacher, must be knowledgeable, sincerely love their profession, feel music and words from the heart, be skillful enough to fully understand the text of the work and its melody, and convey every word that comes out of their mouth to the listening student.

Classical music performance and attitude to musical heritage are the most exemplary aspects of Komiljon Otaniyozov's work. No matter which classical music model he learned from, he attaches great importance to preserving the style of that teacher. In particular, the performance of epics in the style of Bola Bakhshi Abdullayev, the restraint in the style of Hojikhon Boltayev, and the

singing of continuous melodies are all distinguished by their uniqueness. In particular, one of the masters, Komiljon Otaniyozov, diligently masters the ways of Khorezm suvora. On the basis of this, he is able to create his own "Suvora", which can show all his skills. This work was imprinted in the hearts of our people under the name "Suvorai Komil" and took its place in the musical heritage. Komiljon Otaniyozov created more than a thousand melodies and songs in the field of musical creativity. His compositional output, dedicated to various topics, is very wide and colorful. During his artistic career, the master worked closely with famous artists and composers (such as Sultan Hayitbayev, Abdusharif Otajonov, Matniyoz Yusupov), which allowed him to create stage works. Because the master skillfully uses melodies and folk songs that vividly create their inner world in expressing the realities and images in the works. His attitude to the works of classical poets was unparalleled. The poems and ghazals of Saadi, Hafiz Shirozi, Navoi, Ogahi, Mashrab, Fuzuli, and the songs he composed on the wisdom of Makhtumkuli, Kamina, and Mullanafas are distinguished by their originality. The master's pen, which he used in poetry, also stands out among literary figures for its sharp thinking. At first, he wrote poems under the pseudonym "Komiy", later "Komil".

Bul voyaga yetkazgan, rahmatim ko'p vatanga,
Minnatdorlik bildiray, xalqimga, do'st-yoringa,
Yetim edim asrading, ulg'aydim, g'ani bo'ldim,
Ilm-u hunarlar berdi, baxtli davronim menga.

Mehnatim ko'p yoshlikda, podachilik kasbinda,
Mehnat evazi hurmat davlatim berdi menga.
Maktab ochib ko'zimni, ustozlar ilgin tutdim,
Ma'rifatni o'rgatdi, rahnamo bo'ldi menga.

Ustozlarimni desam, Abdukarim, Matpano,
To'ychi hofiz, Sheroziy, Yunus aka pir menga.
To'xtasin-u Halima, Karim Zokir, Mukarram,
Bola baxshi, Lutfixon, Zuhrlar ustoz menga.

Otaullo eshon-u Hojixon-u Jo'raxon,
Ma'mur hofiz, Matkarim, Akbar qori fan menga.
Mandan oldin kim kelsa, go'zal san'at ichinda,

Barchasini pesh tutdim, bo'ldi hodiroh menga.
Baxtimni ochgan elim, do'stlarim bor mard belim,
Komil huquq ong berdi, baxtli zamonim menga.

We can conclude from these lines that through the works of Komiljon Ataniyozov, we can educate young people in the spirit of love for the homeland, cherishing every inch of it, respect for teachers, and loyalty to the ideals of independence. Komiljon Ataniyozov is an outstanding poet and artist of Uzbekistan, one of the largest representatives of our national musical heritage. His work plays a significant role in expressing the culture and national traditions of our people, enriching Uzbek art. His importance in the education of young people can be seen in the following aspects:

Increasing national pride: Through the work of K. Ataniyozov, young people get acquainted with the culture, historical values, and traditions of their people. The songs he created awaken love for their country in young people, feeling the national spirit and pride.

Spirituality and moral education: Hafiz's works express human values, kindness, and humanitarian ideas. For example, in his works such as "Doston" and "Mother's Heart", great emphasis is placed on respect for parents and human relationships. This forms spiritual maturity and morality in the upbringing of young people.

Arousing interest in musical education and art: The melodies and songs in his works increase interest in our national instruments and musical genres. Through Otaniyozov's songs, young people learn not only to listen to music, but also to understand it deeply. This contributes to the development of musical education and art.

Strengthening the sense of patriotism: Komiljon Otaniyozov's works, which reflect the pain and dreams of his people, instill in young people feelings such as love for the Motherland, loyalty, and selflessness. Songs like "El-yurtga khizmat" strengthen the spirit of serving one's homeland.

Creative inspiration and cultural upliftment: Through the work of Otaniyozov, young people have the opportunity to study examples of folk art and enter their spiritual world. This encourages them to be creative and leads to their own cultural upliftment.

In general, the work of Komiljon Otaniyozov plays a significant role in the upbringing of young people, glorifying national values, and helping them grow

into mature individuals. By listening to and studying his works, young people understand their identity and learn to look at art and life with a positive outlook.

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